

DJANGO FRAMEWORK PLATFORMASIDA SODDA WEB ILOVA YARATISH

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Djangoning asosiy maqsadi ma'lumotlar bazasiga asoslangan murakkab web-saytlarni yaratishni yengillashtirish hisoblanadi. Ushbu freymvork komponentlarning qayta ishlatilishi va „ulanishi“, tez rivojlanishi va o'zingizni takrorlamaslik tamoyiliga urg'u beradi.[4] Python, hatto sozlash fayllari va ma'lumotlar modellari uchun ham qo'llaniladi. Django shuningdek, yaratish, o'qish, yangilash va o'chirish uchun qo'shimcha admin interfeysini taqdim etadi, bu introspeksiya orqali dinamik ravishda yaratiladi hamda boshqaruv modellari yordamida sozlanadi.

Djangodan foydalanadigan ba'zi taniqli saytlarga PBS,[5] Instagram,[6] Mozilla,[7] The Washington Times,[8] Disqus,[9] Bitbucket[10] va Nextdoor[11] kiradi. Django ning yaratuvchilari Tahrirlash Russell Keith-Magee ,Adrian Holovaty , Simon Willison, Jacob Kaplan-Moss , Wilson Miner

Django so'zining o'zi esa fransuz jazz musiqachisi Reynxard Django sharafiga qo'yilgan. Uning asl ismi Jan Batist Renart bo'lib, taxallusi Django bo'lgan. Bu so'z sigan tilida „men uyg'ondim“ degan ma'noni anglatadi.

Django backend vositasi sifatida

Manbalar Tahrirlash

↑ „FAQ: General - Django documentation - Django“. Qaraldi: 30-aprel 2016-yil.

↑ „FAQ: General - Django documentation - Django“. Qaraldi: 30-aprel 2016-yil.

↑ Adrian Holovaty, Jacob Kaplan-Moss. The Django Book. „Django follows this MVC pattern closely enough that it can be called an MVC framework“ Wayback Machine saytida arxivlandi (2016-09-02).

↑ „Design Philosophies“. Django. Qaraldi: 18-mart 2018-yil.

↑ „20 Creative Websites Running Django“. 14-iyun 2013-yilda asl nusxadan arxivlandi. Qaraldi: 24-iyul 2020-yil.

↑ „What Powers Instagram: Hundreds of Instances, Dozens of Technologies“.

↑ „Python“. Mozilla Developer Network. 8-fevral 2012-yilda asl nusxadan arxivlandi. Qaraldi: 30-aprel 2016-yil. Wayback Machine saytida arxivlandi (2012-02-08).

↑ Opensource.washingtontimes.com. Retrieved on 2014-05-30.

↑ „Scaling Django to 8 Billion Page Views“.

↑ „Django Success Story Bitbucket – Django“. 20-aprel 2016-yilda asl nusxadan arxivlandi. Qaraldi: 30-aprel 2016-yil. Wayback Machine saytida arxivlandi (2016-04-20).

↑ „The anti-Facebook: one in four American neighborhoods are now using this private social network“. The Verge. Qaraldi: 16-iyun 2016-yil.

Django nima va u qanday ishlaydi?

Django - python dasturlash tilida veb ilovalar ishlab chiqish uchun ajoyib freymvork. Freymvork python dasturlash tilida yozilgan. Django freymvorki birinchi bor 2005-yil 21-iyulda ishga tushirilgan. Loyihani ishlab chiquvchilari Django Software Foundationdir va loyiha ular tomonidan qo'llab-quvvatlanadi. Dasturchilar: Rasl Keyt Magi, Adrian Holovaty, Saymon Vilson, Yakob Kaplan Moss, Uilson Mayner. Freymvork

krossplatformalidir(ya'ni barcha operatsion tizimlarni qo'llab quvvatlaydi). Django yaratilgan sayt bir yoki bir nechta ilovalardan tashkil topishi mumkin. Bu esa freymvorkning arxitekturasini boshqalaridan farqli jihatidir (Misol uchun:Ruby on Rails).

Xulosa: Django bu veb freymvork.

Freymvorkning ishlash prinsplaridan biri bu - DRY (Don't repeat yourself- "o'z-o'zingni takrorlarma"). Bu degani, siz sayt yozish davomida siz "velosiped"ni qaytadan ixtiro qilmaysiz, u siz uchun tayyor. Ya'ni bir kodni qaytadan yozishga hojat yo'q, bu esa veb ilovani yaratilish protsessini tezlashtiradi

Boya aytib o'tganimdek, Django 2005-yilda ishlab chiqildi va shu vaqtdan boshlab bosqichma-bosqich eng yaxshi freymvorklar qatoridan o'rin egalladi. Freymvork dasturchilarning muammolarini bir necha daqiqa mobaynida hal etib bermoqda. Django veb ilovalarning yozilish jarayonini sezilarli darajada yengillashtirdi va veb ilovalar yaratish uchun ajoyib, soddalashtirilgan yo'lni taqdim eta oldi.

Freymvork MVC loyihalashtirish shablonidan foydalanadi:

MVC - "Model View Controller" ya'ni : Model(model- ma'lumotlarni o'zida saqlaydi va controller buyruqlariga asoslanib o'z holatini o'zgaritiradi),View (ko'rinish yoki interfeys - ma'lumotlarning tashqi ko'rinishini ta'minlaydi), Controller(boshqaruvchi -ya'ni foydalanuvchi harakatlarini interpretatsiya qiladi)

MODEL - Djangoning rasmiy qo'llanmasida(django documentation) model bu "ma'lumotlarning manbasi" ekanligi haqida aytilgan. U o'zida kalit so'zlar va ma'lumotlarni saqlaydi. Qisqa qilib aytganda ma'lumotlar "jadval" ko'rinishida saqlanadi va buning uchun Django:PostgreSQL, MySQL, SQLite va Oracle kabi ma'lumotlar omborlarini qo'llab quvvatlaydi.

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Django dasturlash tilini o'rganishda obyektlar va obyektga murojaatning ahamiyati katta. Django frameworki ham obyektariyentlangan dasturlash prinsiplariga asoslangan, shuning uchun bu prinsiplarni tushunish va amalga oshirish juda muhimdir.

Django dasturlash tilini o'rganishda, "models" nomli modul orqali obyektlar yaratiladi. Bu obyektlar ma'lumotlar bazasidagi jadvalga mos keladi. Jadvalning har bir qatorini "object" deb nomlash mumkin. Masalan, "Student" nomli jadvalni tuzish uchun quyidagi kod yoziladi:

```
from django.db import models
class Student(models.Model):
    name = models.CharField(max_length=100)
    age = models.IntegerField()
    grade = models.FloatField()
```

Bu kodda, "Student" nomli obyekt yaratiladi, unda "name", "age" va "grade" xususiyatlari mavjud. "CharField", "IntegerField" va "FloatField" kabi maydonlar ma'lumot turlarini belgilaydilar.

Obyektning xususiyatlariga murojaat uchun nuqta operatoridan foydalaniladi. Masalan:

```
student1 = Student(name="John", age=20, grade=3.5)
print(student1.name) # John
print(student1.age) # 20
```

Obyektning funksiyalariga murojaat uchun esa obyekt nomi orqali funksiya chaqiriladi. Masalan:

```
student1.save() # Ma'lumotlar bazasiga saqlash
```

Django dasturlash tilini o'rganishda obyektga murojaatning yanada ko'proq tushunilishi va amalga oshirilishi kerak, chunki bu prinsiplar Django frameworki ichidagi bir nechta funksiyalarning asosiy qismi hisoblanadi.

Django dasturlash tilini o'rganishning muhim qismlaridan biri obyektariyentlangan dasturlash prinsiplarini tushunish va amalga oshirishdir. Bu prinsiplar asosan obyektarga va obyektga murojaatga asoslanadi. Django frameworki ham bu prinsiplarga asoslanganligi uchun, obyektlar va obyektga murojaatning ko'proq tushunilishi va amalga oshirilishi kerak. "models" nomli modul orqali obyektlar yaratiladi va bu obyekt ma'lumotlar bazasidagi jadvalga mos keladi. Obyektning xususiyatlariga nuqta operatoridan foydalaniladi va funksiyalariga esa obyekt nomi orqali murojaat qilinadi. Django dasturlash tilini o'rganish uchun, obyektga murojaatning yanada ko'proq tushunilishi va amalga oshirilishi kerak, chunki bu prinsiplar Django frameworki ichidagi bir nechta funksiyalarning asosiy qismi hisoblanadi.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar:

- 1G'ulomov S.S. va boshqalar "Axborot tizimlari va texnologiyalari" .Oliy o'quv yurti talabalari uchun darslik. Toshkent-"Sharq"- 2000. 529 b.
- 2Juraev, Muzaffarjon Mansurjonovich. "Prospects for the development of professional training of students of professional educational institutions using electronic educational resources in the environment of digital transformation." *Academia Globe: Inderscience Research* 3.10 (2022): 158-162.
- 3Juraev, Muzaffarjon Mansurjonovich. "The value of open mass competitions in the process of digitalization of extracurricular activities of schoolchildren." *Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal* 3.10 (2022): 338-344.
- 4Jo'rayev, Muzaffarjon. "Professional ta'lim jarayonida fanlararo uzvilik va uzliksizlikni ta'minlash o'quvchilari kasbiy tayyorgarligining muhim omili sifatida." *Zamonaviy dunyoda amaliy fanlar: Muammolar va yechimlar* 1.29 (2022): 43-46.
- 5Juraev, M. M. "OA Qo'ysinov Description of the methodological basis for ensuring interdisciplinary continuity of the subject "Computer Science and Information Technology" in vocational education." *JournalNX-A Multidisciplinary Peer Reviewed* 7.10 (2021).
- 6Mansurjonovich, Juraev Muzaffarjon. "Description of the Methodological Basis for Ensuring Interdisciplinary Continuity of the Subject" *Computer Science and Information TECHNOLOGY" in Vocational Education.* *JournalNX* 7.10: 223-225.
- 7Khasanov, A. R. (2022). LEARNING IS A COMPETENCY-BASED APPROACH AS A CONTENT UPDATE STEP. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 10(12), 217-223.
- 8Khasanov, A. R. (2022). Development of information competence of future informatics teachers as a pedagogical problem. *Open Access Repository*, 9(12), 73-79.
9. Xasanov, A. R. (2021, May). USE OF MODERN PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES AND INTERACTIVE METHODS IN TEACHING COMPUTER SCIENCE. In *E-Conference Globe* (pp. 198-199).
- 10Mansurjonovich, Juraev Muzaffarjon. "CURRENT STATUS OF THE SCIENCE OF INFORMATICS AND INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES IN THE PROFESSIONAL EDUCATION SYSTEM, EXISTING PROBLEMS AND SOLUTIONS, PRINCIPLES AND CONTENT OF THE SCIENCE ORGANIZATION." *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal* 10.12 (2022): 327-331.
- 11Mansurjonovich, Juraev Muzaffarjon. "Professional Educational Institutions Theoretical and Practical Basis of Development of the Content of Pedagogical Activity of Teachers of" *Information and Information Technologies*." *Open Access Repository* 9.12 (2022): 85-89.
- 12Mansurjonovich, Juraev Muzaffarjon. "Experience Of Cambridge Curricula In Ensuring The Continuity Of Curricula In The Field Of "Computer Science And Information Technology" In The System Of Professional Education." *The American Journal of Interdisciplinary Innovations and Research* 3.11 (2021): 26-32.
- 13Juraev, Muzaffarjon Mansurjonovich. "Theoretical and practical principles of improving the content of the pedagogical activity of ICT teachers of professional educational institutions in the conditions of information of education." (2022).
- 14Juraev, Muzaffarjon Mansurjonovich. "Methodological foundations for improving the content of training future ict teachers in the conditions of digital transformation of education." (2022): 9-11.

15Melikyzievich, Siddikov Ilkhom, et al. "THE METHOD OF REFERENCE TESTS FOR THE DIAGNOSIS OF DIGITAL DEVICES." International Journal of Early Childhood Special Education 14.7 (2022).

16Mansurjonovich, Juraev Muzaffarjon. "Designing an electronic didactic environment to ensure interdisciplinary integration in the teaching of" Informatics and information technologies" during professional education." Confrencea 11.11 (2023): 78-82.

17Mansurjonovich, Juraev Muzaffarjon, and Aroyev Dilshod Davronovich. "INTERDISCIPLINARY INTEGRATION IS AN IMPORTANT PART OF DEVELOPING THE PROFESSIONAL TRAINING OF STUDENTS." Open Access Repository 9.1 (2023): 93-101.

18Juraev, M. M. "ZY Xudoyberdiyev Theoretical analysis of the continuity model of computer science and information technology in the System of professional education." European Scholar Journal (ESJ)//ISSN (E): 2660-5562.

19Xudayberdiyev, Zayniddin Yavkachevich, and Muzaffarjon Mansurjonovich Juraev. "Theoretical analysis of the continuity model of computer science and information technology in the system of professional education." (2021).

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